

**ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DEVELOPING RESEARCH
METHODOLOGIES****Mirasol Pamittan-Gabaran**

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) becomes the global technological phenomenon for its highly advanced prompts that significantly shape knowledge development and information processing system across the world. This study described and examined the roles of Artificial Intelligence in the development of Research Methodologies based from the perceptions of teacher-researchers among selected public schools in the Philippines. The study used descriptive correlational research design and utilized a researcher-made survey-questionnaire. Further, the study was participated by 350 randomly selected public school teachers in the Philippines. Results of the study revealed that teachers highly perceived that Artificial Intelligence roles as innovative technological platform for data collection and management, data analysis and research design formulation. On the other hand, the study showed that teachers encountered several challenges in using Artificial Intelligence as it is difficult to navigate its bias detection features, reproducibility and documentation and reporting. Apparently, the study found out that there was a positive relationship between teachers' perceptions on the roles of Artificial Intelligence in developing research methodologies in terms of data collection management and the challenges encountered by teachers in using Artificial Intelligence in formulating research methodologies in terms of bias detection features which suggested that teachers who perceived AI as significant tool for managing the data were also likely to experience concerns about the biases that may arise from its use. Thus, the study developed an intervention program that may help teachers deepen their understanding in the use of AI for the development, selection and presentation of research methodologies for quality-based educational researches.

Keywords:

role, Artificial Intelligence, research, methodologies, challenges, perceptions, teachers

INTRODUCTION

Research in education is a discipline that enables educators and policy-makers undertake in order to address the prevailing problems, needs and concerns relative to education and its allied discipline. Conducting research is an imperative scholarly work which teachers, learners, school heads and education officials are expected to undertake in order to create impactful contributions in the body of knowledge. As the modern technological landscape directly influences education, modern day scholars and researchers in education are using and adapting different technological platform in formulating and completing their research work. The use of different technological platforms enable researchers to complete their research work without consuming so much time and also, obtain accuracy and consistency specially when they apply different modern devices in statistical calculations. In this regard, modern scholars including teachers are also navigating the use of modern tools in developing research. One of the actual conditions which researchers frequently encounter is the proper selection and use of research methodologies in developing their research work. Apparently, teachers also pose difficulty in choosing relevant methodologies because of the different interpretations and appreciations in the

use of different forms of methodologies in education-related researches. The proper selection and use of research methodologies are critical element to obtain an overall success, accuracy and coherence of a research work.

On one hand, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a new innovative technological machine which generates prompts and ideas instantaneously. At the core of this modern tool which generates information, ideas, mathematical calculations and the like, it has been used for wider scholarly work which help learners, teachers and other scholars complete their work in fast-paced manner. Apparently, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the capability of computational systems to perform tasks commonly associated with human intelligence. This technological breakthrough offers an intellectual process of humans, the ability to reason, discover meaning and the like. In this way, many scholars specially teachers are now utilizing Artificial Intelligence (AI) as support tool for generating ideas and collect information relative to their academic work. In the Philippine educational settings, the use of Artificial Intelligence in generating ideas and inputs for the development of teaching strategies, methods and styles is apparent. Teachers commonly seek digital support under this modern tool in order to expand their understanding to wider instructional processes opportunities. However, several conditions pose academic risk in using Artificial Intelligence (AI) specially in conducting a research work. As research work contains highly scientific and technical aspects, many teachers are slowly becoming dependent on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) who in their capacities, maximize the use of Artificial Intelligence not only in the formulation of their research topics but also, they extend its use even it generating statistical interpretations, analysis and discussions.

The role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the conduct of a research work specifically among education-related researches has not been put into serious concerns in the academic community. There are less published researches that directly focused on the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the formulation, construction and administration of a research work. In this line, the researchers observed that most number of teachers and their learners who undertake their research works are significantly dependent on the use of Artificial Intelligence which most often than not, poses greater risk as to the credibility and accuracy of their researches conducted. Also, researchers observed that when Artificial Intelligence has been used for research purposes, many teachers fail to follow the technical procedures and analytical manner of presenting the credence of their researches. Artificial Intelligence's (AI) system leverage machine learning and adaptability, curriculum and content. Thus, AI has been adopted and used in education (Su & Yang, 2022). The development of AI in education has been developing to empower learners and enabled them to reflect on learning based on data-driven and personalized learning acquisition processes (Ouyang & Jiao, 2023). The emergence of Artificial Intelligence and its progressively wider impact has instituted a consensus-based expert elicitation process. The fast development of AI needs to be supported by the necessary regulatory insight for AI-based technologies specially in conducting scholarly works (Mhlanga, 2023). Further, integration of Artificial Intelligence in research and development leverages large datasets and identify patterns to surpass human performance (Alowais,2023). Also, there are several limitations when using AI in research including generalizability, dependence on data quality and diversity, lack of domain expertise, limited ability to understand context, ethical considerations and limited to general original insights.

The researchers find a strong knowledge gap forming a research gap among the previous studies conducted whereas they find that most of published researchers are purely focused on the assessment of Artificial Intelligence's effectiveness. In this line, they fail to significantly describe and examine the role of Artificial Intelligence in selecting and developing research methodologies. Thus, this study aimed to fill this research gap. Also, the study is significant as it may provide scientific data relative to the roles of AI in developing research methodologies for teacher-researchers. Thus, a proposed intervention program is presented which can be used in order to develop or sustain teachers' proper use of Artificial Intelligence in the development of research methodologies in administering education-related researches.

OBJECTIVES

This study described and examined public school teachers' perceptions on the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in developing research methodologies. Specifically, the study described teachers' perceptions on the role of AI in developing research methodologies in terms of data collection and management, data analysis and research design formulation. Further, the study described the challenges encountered by teachers in using AI in developing research methodologies in terms of bias detection features, reproducibility and documentation and reporting. In addition, the study examined if there would be a significant relationship between teachers'

perceptions on the roles of AI in developing research methodologies and the challenges encountered by teachers in using AI in the formulation of research methodologies. Apparently, the study proposed an intervention program which may teachers to develop or sustain teachers' proper use of Artificial Intelligence in the development of research methodologies in administering education-related researches.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive correlational research design in order to describe and examine public school teachers' perceptions on the roles of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in developing research methodologies. In addition, the study used simple random sampling technique to select the participation of 350 public school teachers among selected public schools in the Philippines. Thus, researchers developed a survey-questionnaire which contained two (2) parts. Under part 1, it contained items relating to the teachers' perceptions on the roles of Artificial Intelligence in developing research methodologies. Also, under part 2, it contains items relating to the challenges encountered by teachers in using AI in the development of research methodologies as they conducted education-related researches. The researcher-made survey-questionnaire was subjected to validation and reliability test specifically through the conduct of pilot test. Expert-validators who were selected by the researchers comprising by three (3) Graduate School Professors, marked that the developed survey-questionnaire was highly acceptable and coherent. Thus, the results of reliability test showed that items under part 1 gained a Cronbach Alpha result of .819 and items under part 2 gained a Cronbach Alpha result of .912 which both signified that the developed survey-questionnaire was acceptable. Further, the researchers used a 4-Likert Scale whereas items under part 1 were rated through: 4-highly perceived, 3-perceived, 2-slightly perceived and 1-not perceived. On the other hand, items under part 2 were rated through: 4-always encountered, 3-often encountered, 2-seldom encountered and 1-not encountered. Apparently, the study used formal communication letters which formally invited the participation of the respondents. Also, they distributed informed consent in order to solicit the deliberate participation of their respondents in this study. Hence, researchers floated their survey-questionnaire using a Google Form where link was sent to the personal email addresses of the respondents. As to the data analysis techniques used by the researchers, they employed mean, standard deviation and general weighted mean to describe teachers' perceptions on the role of AI in developing research methodologies and similar statistical tools were used in order to describe the challenges encountered by the respondents in using AI in the development of research methodologies. Thus, Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was used in order to examine if there would be a significant relationship between teachers' perceptions on the roles of AI in developing research methodologies and the challenges they encountered in using AI in the formulation of research methodologies. Also, the researchers stored the data gathered on their personal devices and destroyed the same when this paper reached its finality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Creating and developing impactful educational researches become one of the major concerns of teachers as they are less engaged into research and development undertaking. Their less engagement is commonly factored in by their instructional workloads in their respective schools. However, while they are not fully engaged in research and development, still they were expected to develop a highly credible education-related researches that may help their institutions and the department at large, to formulate research-based programs and instruction which can eventually help the system to obtain quality-based education. In this regard, when Artificial Intelligence has been introduced and used by scholars, there are different perceptions, controversies and academic-related concerns emerged on the basis of its roles in producing accurate, comprehensive and highly impactful educational researches.

- 1. Teachers' Perceptions on the Roles of Artificial Intelligence in Developing Research Methodologies.** The result showed that teachers highly perceived artificial intelligence as modern tool which helped teachers select and develop appropriate research methodologies. The results revealed that data collection management obtained a highest mean of 3.82, described as highly perceived while data analysis gained a mean of 3.78 and research design formulation obtained a mean of 3.72, both described as highly perceived. The results showed that teachers have strong positive perceptions on the role of Artificial Intelligence in developing research methodologies. The results further implied that teachers find Artificial Intelligence as an effective tool in organizing and managing their gathered data efficiently. This showed teachers highly perceived the crucial roles of AI in data collection procedures

which formed a foundational aspect in educational researches. Following closely is the data analysis where the results implied that teachers highly perceived the role of Artificial Intelligence to derive meaningful and scientific insights based from the actual research findings. On one hand, teachers also highly perceived the role of Artificial Intelligence in helping them conceptualize and structure their research works. The results on teachers' perceptions on the AI's roles in developing research methodologies indicated that teachers integrate this modern tool so that they could obtain accuracy and in-depth discussion of researchers' insights. Results of the study supported the study of Chounta et al. (2022) which concluded that Artificial Intelligence served as support tool in creating more efficient and effective research work and instructional practices.

2. **Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Using Artificial Intelligence in Developing Research Methodologies.** The result showed that teachers frequently struggled in using Artificial Intelligence. The result further showed that bias detection features obtained the highest mean of 3.32, described as always encountered. On one hand, reproducibility and documentation and reporting both gained mean scores of 3.28, described as always encountered. Accordingly, the results implied that teachers faced significant challenges when using Artificial Intelligence (AI) in developing research methodologies with high frequency of struggles encountered. The findings further revealed that teachers always encountered difficulties in determining and mitigating biases within the Artificial Intelligence systems as produced by its prompts and generated ideas. This underlying challenge encountered by teachers raised concern as bias in research which could potentially lead to skewed results and defeat the integrity of the research work. On one hand, as to reproducibility and documentation and reporting, indicated that teachers frequently struggled in using Artificial Intelligence as they experienced difficulty in holding the reliability threshold of generated prompts. Hence, the results on the challenges encountered by teachers in using Artificial Intelligence indicated the occurrence of potential barriers that hampered teachers to create more credible researches. Apparently, the study implicated that teachers should fully leverage AI's capabilities in developing research while sensitively imposing meticulous analysis and detailed-oriented behavior in deducing ideas or prompts provided by AI.
3. **Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Perceptions on the Roles of AI in Developing Research Methodologies and the Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Using AI.** The results showed that there was a positive correlation between teachers' perceptions on the roles of Artificial Intelligence in developing research methodologies in terms of data collection management and the challenges encountered by teachers in using Artificial Intelligence in formulating research methodologies in terms of bias detection features ($r=.421$). Thus, the null hypothesis that there would be significant relationship between teachers' perceptions on the roles of Artificial Intelligence in developing research methodologies in terms of data collection management and the challenges encountered by teachers in using Artificial Intelligence in formulating research methodologies in terms of bias detection features was rejected. The results suggested that as teachers recognize the benefits of Artificial Intelligence in streamlining, organizing and collecting the data, they became more aware of the challenges associated with bias detection in Artificial Intelligence systems. The results also implied that teachers who perceived AI as significant tool for managing the data were also likely to experience concerns about the biases that may arise from its use. Results of the study supported the study of Mehdaoui (2024) which concluded that there was a positive association between the Artificial Intelligence's use in formulating research and the external barriers to better align technological innovations. The study practically implicated that teachers should invest on attending programs and workshops relative to the use of Artificial Intelligence in research. Thus, school heads should also provide school-based trainings through LAC sessions to elevate teachers understanding on the use of Artificial Intelligence in the conduct of educational researches. Thus, the study further implicated that teachers should pose a balanced perspective so that they could potentially harness the effective use of AI in research methodologies while ensuring the integrity and reliability of their researches' findings.
4. **Proposed Intervention Program.** Based from the findings, school heads, teaches and other focal persons concerned should formulate workshops and training sessions to instill founded understanding among teachers the use of AI in developing research methodologies and administering research work

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under their respective disciplines. Also, school heads and teachers should spearhead collaborative learning communities through the formation of groups and pairing where expert teacher-researchers can share their experiences, challenges and strategies related to using AI in research.

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CONCLUSION

Teachers highly perceived that Artificial Intelligence roles as innovative technological platform for data collection and management, data analysis and research design formulation. On the other hand, the study showed that teachers encountered several challenges in using Artificial Intelligence as it is difficult to navigate its bias detection features, reproducibility and documentation and reporting. Apparently, the study found out that there was a positive relationship between teachers' perceptions on the roles of Artificial Intelligence in developing research methodologies in terms of data collection management and the challenges encountered by teachers in using Artificial Intelligence in formulating research methodologies in terms of bias detection features which suggested that teachers who perceived AI as significant tool for managing the data were also likely to experience concerns about the biases that may arise from its use.

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